

A More Effective Way to Communicate With the Deaf Seeking Health Care in Urgent Care

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Background

- Hearing loss a \$980 billion global problem
- The Deaf and Hard of Hearing (Deaf/HH) are marginalized
- The Deaf/HH have compromised health care
- Most Deaf/HH do not understanding providers instructions
- Reducing language barriers could prevent 671,440 adverse events

Problem

The Deaf/HH individuals seeking urgent care do not understand:

- Hearing medical providers/personnel
- Informed consent
- Treatment
- Medications, and discharge instructions

Purpose

Develop and implement a tailored protocol for using video remote interpreter (VRI) technology in urgent care settings, complemented by a two-minute educational video to enhance healthcare providers' communication strategies, interpersonal skills, self-reflection, and awareness for better interactions with Deaf/HH patients

Methods

- **Design:** A quality improvement, pre/post-test measured change in providers knowledge of themselves, change agent, improved communication with Deaf/HH
- **Setting:** Two urgent care clinics in Southern California
- **Participants:** 14 Mid-Levels
- **Theory/Framework:** Hildegard Peplau/Cheryl Stetler
- **Data collection:** pre/post-test surveys via Qualtrics

American Sign Language (ASL) a Beautiful Visual Language

Effective communication begins with language

Results

- 14 participants
- 8 males and 6 females
- 58.33% of providers had a Master's degree
- 46.15% of providers were not comfortable treating Deaf/HH
- 15.38% of providers rarely treated Deaf/HH

Theory and Framework

- **Peplau's Theory:** A provider must promote interpersonal-therapeutic-communicative relationships with every patient
- **Stetler's Framework:** The model of research utilization helps the advanced practice nurse (APN) to think critically and reflect on practice to create formal change within an organization by applying research with evidence-based practice

Limitations

- Small sample size
- Time constraints within the DNP program restricted implementation of VRI

Recommendations

- Educate providers/staff on Deaf/HH culture
- Implement Deaf /HH SOP in all urgent cares
- Implement VRI in all urgent cares
- Incorporate ASL communication and best practices into PA/NP educational programs

References

